

Ex-post Dissemination and Communication Strategy & Plan

Deliverable 7.6

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D7.6: Ex-post Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Plan

Summary

This document details the ex-post dissemination and communication strategy of the project B-WaterSmart. It identifies the main objectives of the communication and dissemination activities that were followed throughout the project and will continue to be pursued after its terminus and puts forward the actions targeted at six kinds of audiences: Strategic water managers; Technical water managers; Decision & policy makers, regulators; Scientific community; Citizens; International, European and national networks, clusters, multipliers, and stakeholder groups. Ex-post dissemination ensures that results that have been developed and are ready to be used are widely distributed. It enhances the chances for the project to have real impact and promotes the transfer of innovation. It allows best practices to be shared and replicated by relevant key actors.

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Dissemination level

- PU = Public
- PP = Restricted to other programme participants
- RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium.
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- CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

Table of contents

List of Figures.....	3
List of Tables	4
Executive summary.....	5
1. Introduction to the project context	6
2. Dissemination and communication objectives.....	7
3. Communication	10
3.1 Project identity.....	10
3.2 Communication aimed at strategic and technical water managers	12
3.3 Communication aimed at policy makers and regulators	13
3.4 Communication aimed at the networks, clusters, multipliers and stakeholder groups	14
3.5 Communication aimed at citizens and the general public.....	14
3.6 Communication aimed at the scientific community	15
4. Dissemination.....	16
4.1 Dissemination aimed at strategic and technical water managers.....	16
4.2 Dissemination aimed at policy makers and regulators	17
4.3 Dissemination aimed at the networks, clusters, multipliers and stakeholder groups	18
4.4 Dissemination aimed at citizens and the general public	18
4.5 Dissemination aimed at the scientific community	18

List of Figures

Figure 1 B-WaterSmart logo.....	10
Figure 2 Banner of the Cirseau Policy Campaign.....	13

List of Tables

Table 1 Deliverables.....	8
Table 2 Milestones	9

Executive summary

This document details the ex-post dissemination and communication strategy of the project B-WaterSmart. It identifies the main objectives of the communication and dissemination activities that were followed throughout the project and will continue to be pursued after its terminus and puts forward the actions targeted at six kinds of audiences: Strategic water managers; Technical water managers; Decision & policy makers, regulators; Scientific community; Citizens; International, European and national networks, clusters, multipliers, and stakeholder groups. Ex-post dissemination ensures that results that have been developed and are ready to be used are widely distributed. It enhances the chances for the project to have real impact and promotes the transfer of innovation. It allows best practices to be shared and replicated by relevant key actors.

1. Introduction to the project context

A water-smart economy and society is geared towards avoiding water scarcity and pollution, increasing resilience to climate change, and managing water-related risks. The EU-funded B-WaterSmart project aimed to speed up the transition to water-smart economies and societies in coastal Europe and beyond. To achieve this, it adopted a large-scale systemic innovation approach to select, connect, and demonstrate a tailored suite of technology, management and smart data solutions for multiple users and sectors. It endeavoured to create new business models based on circular economy and water-smartness. The project delivered a new framework for evaluating gains in water-smartness and sustainability at different scales. It also demonstrated a range of promising technologies for water reuse and nutrient recovery as well as smart data applications for more efficient resource allocation and use and finally identified further additional application opportunities for these solutions.

For this purpose, we brought together six cities and regions as Living Labs (LL) with high ambitions to address water-related challenges and opportunities – Alicante (ES), Bodø (NO), Flanders (BE), Lisbon (PT), East Frisia (DE), Venice (IT) – selected for complementarity of scale, users, sectors, and challenges, and for opportunities of mutual learning, replication & upscaling through a network of followers already mobilised. We built each case around the actual problem-owner (water utility, municipality), a research partner, innovative solution providers and market-uptake partners (6 are SMEs), complemented by partners with specific crosscutting expertise (social sciences & humanities, IT, business development, water sector outreach). We applied a participatory approach for the co-creation and implementation of solutions through local Communities of Practice (CoP) and a joint innovation alliance of problem owners, as well as developed recommendations for suitable governance models, regulation & policy instruments (Deliverables 5.3, 5.5, 5.6 and 5.8). We delivered a novel framework to assess gains in water-smartness and sustainability at different scales (Deliverable 6.3). Our cases demonstrate in real systems, at multiple scales, a range of promising technologies for water reuse/nutrient recovery, and smart data applications for more efficient, safe allocation & use of resources (water, energy, nutrients). For the apps, we built on FIWARE technology to enable interoperability and exchange across sectors, which is key for systemic change. All cases had defined criteria and target values to achieve by the project end and can build on synergies with other funding opportunities. In this context, the ex-post dissemination and communication strategy will provide an outline for the effective interaction between all involved groups after the end of the project.

2. Dissemination and communication objectives

Dissemination and communication are fundamental activities within research projects to foster actual societal impact and the uptake of research results. The EU defines communication as:

“a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange”¹,

and dissemination as:

“The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.”¹

Ex-post dissemination involves dissemination after the project has finished, when the results have been developed and are ready to be used. It enhances the chances for the project to have real impact and promotes the transfer of innovation. It allows best practices to be shared and replicated by relevant key actors.

The core objectives of the dissemination and communication activities of B-WaterSmart are:

- To maximize project outreach through targeted communication and dissemination activities
- To maximize project impact and exploitation of results by supporting B-WaterSmart solution providers on their route to market beyond the six B-WaterSmart LLS’ areas and beyond Europe (see Deliverables 7.8 and 7.9).
- To link to other projects and initiatives fostering CE and water-smartness in the European water sector, pool results and enable a benchmarking of solutions, assessing their transfer potential.

Dissemination and communication rely on the input from all other WPs and in return feedback into all WPs. It requires a strong articulation between local partners, as well as international ones. This is a task in which all partners of the project collaborated, under the coordination of the WP7 and Task 7.2 leader (IWW). LL mentors were responsible for coordinating the communication and dissemination in each Living Lab. Regular meetings between WP7 partners were held each month. Meeting with LL leaders and mentors were held every three months. Some material, aimed at non-experts, was translated into the languages of the participating countries.

Communication and dissemination activities strived to be inclusive and cater for the specific needs and interests of stakeholders, as well as citizens from diverse backgrounds, taking into consideration gender issues, age group, education level, nationality, and disability, amongst other specific circumstances. All these actions will be guided by the principles of bi-directional communication and co-creation of knowledge, engaging stakeholders and the public in the dissemination and debate of the results produced through this project.

Five main kinds of audiences for the B-WaterSmart project were identified and targeted in communication and dissemination activities:

- Strategic and technical water managers

¹ Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

- Policy makers and regulators
- Networks, clusters, multipliers, and stakeholder groups
- Citizens/general public
- Scientific community

Specific objectives and activities were associated with each target group. A similar strategy will be followed in the ex-post dissemination and communication activities.

Table 1 lists the deliverables of Task 7.2 of Work Package 7 (Connect, communicate, exploit, replicate) and Table 2 its milestones.

Table 1 Deliverables

Number	Title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due date	Status
D7.3	Corporate identity and general communication material	CET	DEC	PU	M6	Delivered
D7.4	Four issues of the project magazine (annual)	IWW	DEC	PU	M48	All issues delivered
D7.5	First version of the dissemination & communication strategy & plan	ICS-UL	R	PU	M6	Delivered
D7.6	Ex-post dissemination & communication strategy & plan	ICS-UL	R	PU	M48	In process

Table 2 Milestones

Number	Title	Lead beneficiary	Due date	Status
MS04	Website and social media channels	IWW	M6	Delivered
MS05	Information needs from CoPs defined	IWW	M6	Delivered
MS11	1st communication campaign about the launch of the knowledge portal	IWW	M13	Delivered
MS14	1st revised version of D7.5 (DCSP)	ICS	M18	Delivered
MS30	Second communication campaign about knowledge portal as key legacy of the project	IWW	M48	Delivered

3. Communication

As mentioned in the prior chapter, we understand communication to refer to promoting the project activities and their results to different audiences, as described in the following subchapters.

Partners compiled email mailing lists of strategic and technical water managers, policy makers and regulators, networks and stakeholder groups, and other interested parties. Publicly available emails of organisations and individual policy makers were directly included in the lists, but in the case of private individual contacts, written consent was sought in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (2016/679) and according to the specific procedures defined in the B-WaterSmart Data Management Plan (D8.3). These contacts will continue to be used to send out updates about the project, invitations for events and publications.

3.1 Project identity

To maintain a cohesive image and make the project and its outputs readily identifiable, a project logo and a corporate design has been created by the partner Cetaqua, through a subcontracted communication agency (Figure 1). This logo is displayed in all project materials, such as the website, social media profiles, leaflets, conference presentations, publications, videos, etc.

Figure 1 B-WaterSmart logo

Concomitantly, templates for Word documents, PowerPoint presentations and publications (such as reports and posters, etc.) were made available for partners. Templates for the LL with partner logos were also produced by partner Cetaqua and made available.

Over the duration of the projects several communication materials were produced and distributed: the project leaflet (containing basic information about the project and its main features, timeline and expected outcomes), two brochures (on the Water Europe Marketplace and the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework), six LL factsheets, four issues of the magazine, 13 posters. These materials were made available online and distributed at water sector events where B-WaterSmart core partners are involved as (co-) organisers (e.g., Water Europe), as well as in scientific and dissemination events and for reaching out to stakeholders.

The logo, the templates, and the other materials will continue to be used as long as there are events, publications and other communication activities connected to the project, after its terminus.

The public project website has been available since Month 3 at: <https://b-watersmart.eu/>. It presents the project, objectives, and LL, and was continuously updated with results and project news (in blog

format). The website contains, among other contents, project materials, press releases, publications, the annual magazine, project results for download, as well as links to social media channels and to the Water Europe Marketplace, developed under B-WaterSmart and other projects: <https://mp.watereurope.eu/>. Links to partner websites and relevant organisations are featured.

The project website will remain online for the next five years. All relevant materials (deliverables, reports, brochures, articles, and others) are being uploaded to Zenodo's EU Open Research Repository, to ensure they will remain accessible after the closure of the website.

Project partners' websites also have mentions to the project that will remain online for a few years after the project's closure. News about project developments, such as new publications, will continue to be shared and promoted at these websites, as well as in newsletters, bulletin boards and other channels of communication. For instance, peer reviewed, popular articles in which KWR is mentioned are stored in the KWR library indefinitely (the KWR library is openly accessible online).

The project maintains and updates profiles on social media: Twitter (@B_WaterSmart) and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/in/b-watersmart-project>). Awareness for the project was raised by using social media (up to weekly updates). Events, publications, and project updates were routinely shared. This will continue as long as there is project news to be shared.

Several videos showcasing the project have been produced and made available in the B-WaterSmart Youtube channel, as well as in other partner organisations channels, and will remain active for the foreseeable future.

3.2 Communication aimed at strategic and technical water managers

Strategic water managers are responsible for planning and aim at saving costs and shifting to more sustainable designs and management techniques, while ensuring reliability and consistency of the selected solutions. They need information on the practical application of research outcomes with a clear focus on the identification of the most appropriate solutions in terms of cost/benefit ratio to a given problem. Technical water managers are responsible for practical application of new technology solutions and are primarily interested in technical details and practical application, focusing on the result of research.

Water managers were one of the key stakeholders of B-WaterSmart, as detailed on D1.1 (CoPs architecture and stakeholder mapping for each LL) of WP1, as well as in Tasks 4.1, 5.1, 7.1 and 7.3. In order not to duplicate and overlap efforts, communication actions have relied on the stakeholder mapping performed in WP1 and followed the guidelines provided in MS3 (WP5), which has resulted in the compilation of a mailing list (following all GDPR rules).

Communication aimed at water managers made use of specific channels and means to convey the project progress:

- The Water Europe Marketplace (Task 7.1)
- CoP session of collaborative work towards the co-creation of water-smartness tools and solutions at the LLs
- Organisation of public local events at the LLs
- Dedicated features in the project newsletter
- Technical and business-oriented articles in the annual project magazine
- Participation in trade fairs and exhibitions.

The Water Europe Marketplace (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/>) was launched in March 2022 and a brochure about it was released in June 2022. The Water Europe Marketplace will remain online after the closure of the project, curated by project partner Water Europe. That way, its longevity is guaranteed and information about B-WaterSmart solutions and demo cases (Living Labs) will be available for a very long time, even after the project website closes down. Project partners' websites and social media channels will continue to promote the marketplace. More details are available in Deliverable D7.8 Final exploitation and business plan for B-WaterSmart solutions and Deliverable D7.2 Long-term business plan and operation model for knowledge portal.

B-WaterSmart will continue to be showcased in trade fairs and other events aimed at water managers. Project partners plan to attend the annual meeting of Aqua Publica Europea, the Water Reuse Europe Conference and Exhibition on Innovation in Water Reuse (Les Sables-D'Olonne; 24-25 Sept. 2024; Presentation Title: "Effects of pre-treatment on membrane performance in industrial wastewater reuse & recycling"), the 3. OSS Symposium" (Münster; 12 Nov 2024; Presentation Title: "Wasserrecycling in Lebensmittel- und Automobilindustrie – Herausforderungen in der Praxis"), the yearly Norsk Vann (the Norwegian Water Authority) conference, the Lisbon Innovation Pathway (October 2024, organised by Aguas do Tejo Atlântico) as well as local events targeting water users (farmers, industries).

3.3 Communication aimed at policy makers and regulators

B-WaterSmart sought to transform innovation results on smart management of water resources into evidence-based practical policy recommendations and communicate them to policy and decision makers. This will be accomplished at different scales (local, regional, national, European, global) and focus on executive material and short content with clear and proven conclusions to improve water management, while fulfilling societal goals, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Communication aimed at policy makers and regulators made use of specific channels and means to convey the project progress:

- Dedicated features in the project newsletter
- Policy oriented articles in the annual project magazine
- Participation in events organised by policy actors and regulators
- Invitations for events organised under the umbrella of the CoP and LLs
- Inclusion of policy makers in CoP from regional and local authorities

To mention here in particular was the CIRSEAU policy campaign in April 2024, where all cluster projects came together for an online campaign, sharing guiding principles and actions for researchers and practitioners and recommendations brief on stakeholder engagement in EU-funded inter- and trans-disciplinary research and innovation projects.

Figure 2 Banner of the Cirseau Policy Campaign

Project members will continue to engage with policy makers after the closure of the project, participating in events by invitation and sending relevant information. Of particular relevance will be the follow-up with replicators that local authorities, partners in this project, will endeavour to pursue.

3.4 Communication aimed at the networks, clusters, multipliers and stakeholder groups

Associations related to water resource management, smart solutions, and water management are key for the dissemination and replication of the methods and technologies implemented in B-WaterSmart. Stakeholders in the water sector include different groups, ranging from water organisations to environmental and consumer organisations. They have different needs and expectations, which include widening the impact of new water solutions developed in the EU. To that end, they need innovative solutions for the water sector to be further replicated in other areas through their communication channels to reach their communities. They require deliverables or materials to improve literacy and awareness on water-related challenges (such as climate change and water scarcity) and the circular economy, driving a better social acceptance of water-smart solutions.

Communication aimed at networks and stakeholder groups made use of specific channels and means to convey the project progress:

- Sending out press releases at key stages of the project
- Dedicated features in the project newsletter
- Targeted articles in the annual project magazine
- Participation in trade fairs and exhibitions
- Invitations for events organised under the aegis of the CoP and LLs

Project members will continue to engage with networks and stakeholder groups after the closure of the project, participating in their events and sending out relevant information since several project members are involved in the Water4all Partnership that will continue its work even after the end of the B-WaterSmart project. Also, there are plans to attend events such as the International Water Association Reuse Conference 2025 (March 2025, Cape Town, South Africa).

3.5 Communication aimed at citizens and the general public

Citizens (or the general public), here considered as all people potentially interested in the project and its outcomes, are another target group for communication and dissemination. Our aim is to increase their level of knowledge around water services, as well as to support citizen awareness and participation to reach acceptance and societal relevance of water-smart solutions.

Besides the communication tools mentioned above (website, social media, leaflet, Marketplace, magazine, newsletter, videos, etc.), the final events of the project will be accompanied by a media campaign. B-WaterSmart partners will continue to collaborate with local and regional media to spread information on the project and the Living Labs.

Also, several partners have planned to maintain or to include B-WaterSmart information in exhibition spaces aimed at the general public: OOWV is showing innovative projects (and will include B-WaterSmart) in the water museum "Kaskade" (at planning stage), Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt VZW will install a notice board at the buffering basin in Hombeek (Belgium) to inform people walking by about the involvement of B-WaterSmart, the space devoted to the dissemination of the B-WaterSmart project at the Water Museum of Alicante will be kept as it is now, at least for two years after the end of the project, and Cetaqua and Aguas de Alicante will promote pilot plant visits even after the end of the project. In addition, ICS-UL is regularly engaged in training programmes aimed at

professional, such as Summer Schools, and high-school students (Ciência Viva; Estágios de Verão da ULisboa), as well as outreach events (Researchers' Night), which will also be an opportunity to communicate about the project results over the coming years.

3.6 Communication aimed at the scientific community

Since that at this stage it is paramount to share the research results with the scientific community, after the closure of the project most efforts will continue to be focused on the dissemination.

Under the aegis of the call that funded B-WaterSmart, a cluster of projects called CIRSEAU was set up. The four other projects encompassed by this cluster are:

- WIDER UPTAKE Achieving wider uptake of water-smart solutions
- ULTIMATE: IndUstry water-utiLiTy symbiosis for a sMarter wATer society solutions
- WATER MINING: Next generation water-smart management systems - large scale demonstrations for a circular economy and society solutions
- REWAISE: REsilient WAter Innovation for Smart Economy solutions

From the very beginning the five coordinators have actively collaborated by starting a process of systematically mapping commonalities in terms of topics, case studies, technologies, methodological frameworks, target regions, and stakeholders. A regular exchange (every three months) between coordinators took place and several cross-cutting topic groups on which ideas are exchanged were formed (on "Communication & Dissemination", "Assessment Frameworks", "Policy & Long-term Impact", "Stakeholder Engagement" and "Young Water Professionals"). Throughout the lifetime of the projects multiple joint activities were organised.

4. Dissemination

Dissemination refers to the public disclosure of the results and therefore it was intensified as the project produced results. Besides sharing project results on the website and the Water Europe Marketplace, the final issue of the magazine, newsletters, and social media, there will be specific activities adjusted to the needs of the target audiences.

4.1 Dissemination aimed at strategic and technical water managers

Dissemination aimed at water managers made use of specific channels and means to promote the use of smart water management tools and convey evidence-based recommendations on best practices, which will be made available on the Water Europe Marketplace (Task 7.1) and partially also on the project website:

- Technical reports
- Factsheets and infographics
- Themed workshops and symposia addressing CE topics.
- Workshops at promising new application sites, where specific exploitation concepts of key B-WaterSmart solutions could be applied (D7.7)
- “Success stories”. Regular presentation and special promotion of selected B-WaterSmart success stories, highlights, and outcomes (beyond deliverables)
- Publications in trade magazines
- Training materials on the website

After the closure of the project, all these publications will remain available at the project website and repositories. Participation in several workshops is also planned, such as a workshop on surface water in February 2025 in which the Bodø kommune was requested to present CoP results.

Water Europe plans to continue building on the BWS results by supporting mature case studies in becoming Water-Oriented Living Labs (WOLLs), stable organisations built to capitalise on the work done and to implement the collaboration and co-creation of strategies and tools for water smartness. Lisbon has already established its WOLL with a ceremony on World Water Day in March 2024. Additionally, the Lisbon Living Lab (LL) was included in the recently published Water4All's ATLAS of WOLLs and had the chance to present its achievements during the official launch of the ATLAS at the World Water Forum in Bali. Lisbon has scheduled a Community of Practice (CoP) meeting of the municipalities (replicators) for October 2024. Venice's WOLL was launched in the final project event in July 2024. Alicante established its WOLL later during the local event co-organised with Water Europe. Flanders is already involved in the Water4All activities with the City of Mechelen. The Mechelen LL is part of the LLs included in the ATLAS and had the chance to present its achievements in Bali. All B-WaterSmart WOLLs will be actively involved in the Water4All Partnership activities and supported in their evolution and maturity, ensuring a long-term impact beyond the project's lifespan.

In the case of EnviroChemie GmbH (Living Lab East Frisia), the transferability of comparable concepts and technologies to other locations and to their digital products has been initiated. The results obtained provide the basis for further large-scale implementations. Next steps are the promotion of their capabilities in the area of water reuse applications (through conferences, exhibitions, and their website). The experience gained with remote control and advanced process control is being

incorporated directly into their WaterExpert product and is already being offered to customers. This will promote the continued implementation of innovative process control that conserves resources and thus leads to an ecological and economic improvement in wastewater treatment.

In the case of the Living Lab Bodo, the municipal authority is studying how to best contact the neighbouring municipalities regarding creating a shared sludge-to-energy biogas reactor. This will most likely be brought up politically in the upcoming years but Bodø kommune needs to decide internally what is the best path forward before bringing the topic to a political level, as well as learning more about what is the best method to proceed. B-WaterSmart is closely tied to the biogas project and will be naturally discussed during these proceedings. The environmental dashboard is currently looking for new municipalities to replicate their dashboard. The Techni smart water meters will undergo a new design based on the feedback from the project and the project partner is interested in upscaling the product for commercial use. This will require certification before upscaling. Nordkontakt and NTNU will discuss more how to incorporate the leakage detection algorithms into the environmental dashboard and NTNU will be continuing their research into future water-smart solutions.

De Watergroep from the Living Lab in Flanders plans to continue their ongoing interaction with stakeholders, primary technical and academy partners (KWR, VMM, Aquafin, Ghent University) with focus on project development for new water smart opportunities and implementation of water smart strategies, developed in B-WaterSmart. KWR is considering a publication on stakeholder engagement for improved uptake of tools, technologies, and solutions, drawing from insights and results from BWS.

4.2 Dissemination aimed at policy makers and regulators

Dissemination aimed at policy makers made use of specific channels and means to convey evidence-based policy recommendations:

- Reports on Policy and Governance Drivers and Barriers for Water-Smart Solutions across 6 Cases (Deliverable D5.3), Drivers and Barriers - Proposal for a New Governance Model (D5.5) and Guidelines and recommendations for regulation and policy instruments (D5.6)
- Policy briefs (Deliverable 5.8, four publications with different topics, including a joint policy brief with CIRSEAU project Water Mining: implementing the water reuse legislation; resources recovery and sludge; energy; large-scale infrastructure implementations), issued by WP5 that summarize policy-relevant project results and revision opportunities for policies in a concise way and suitable for policy makers and decision-makers.
- Hearings - team members sought out to be invited to hearings convened by committees of regional/national parliaments to discuss the results and policy recommendations of the project. This may be achieved by sending the policy briefs to these committees and expressing the willingness to discuss them face-to-face.
- Dissemination articles, based on research results, written in a clear and jargon-free language, aimed at policy makers and other non-specialists.

All the CoPs included policy representatives that were actively involved in the LL meetings.

After the closure of the project, project members are available to continue to attend policy events by invitation. The reports and policy briefs will remain in the project website and in repositories. Since the Policy Briefs will be published during the summer break, they will be actively disseminated from September onwards and sent to relevant policy makers and stakeholders.

4.3 Dissemination aimed at the networks, clusters, multipliers and stakeholder groups

Stakeholders were regularly involved in the project through the LLs and the CoPs. Just as water managers, they will be targeted in forthcoming Water-Oriented Living Labs, workshops, and other initiatives from project partners (see above).

4.4 Dissemination aimed at citizens and the general public

There were several public events held at each LL towards the end of the project to present the project results and to strengthen public interest, citizens' involvement and creating awareness on water-related issues and topics. Whenever possible, other public events will be held, and non-technical materials will be distributed after the closure of the project.

4.5 Dissemination aimed at the scientific community

The three main channels of dissemination of the B-WaterSmart results to the scientific community are conference presentations, articles in peer-reviewed journals (Open Access) and the organisation of events aimed at academic audiences (lectures, seminars, workshops).

Due to the nature and timings of scientific work, it is expected that the dissemination of results to the scientific community will continue in the years after the closure of the project.

B-WaterSmart results will be presented in several scientific conferences throughout 2025 and 2026. For instance, the following abstracts have been submitted by the Lisbon Municipality team:

- Viegas R.M.C., Figueiredo D., Mesquita E., Charrua S., Costa C., Lourinho R., Rosa M.J. (2025). Pilot-scale studies of advanced wastewater treatment for direct potable water reuse for beer production. IWA Reuse 2025. Cape Town, South Africa. March 2025 (submitted)
- Viegas R.M.C., Costa J., Mesquita E., Figueiredo D., Teixeira P., Coelho S.T., Rosa M.J. (2025). Mechanistic modelling of chlorine decay in reclaimed water distribution systems – case study applications. IWA Reuse 2025. Cape Town, South Africa. March 2025 (submitted)
- Figueiredo D., Viegas R.M.C., Mesquita E., Charrua S., Costa C., Lourinho R., Rosa M.J. (2025), A reclamation protocol for water reuse in craft beer. Caminho da Inovação 2024. Lisboa, Portugal. October 2024

Veritas is planning on participating in several national and/or international conferences/symposia (e.g. Ecomondo, IWA, Ecosp, etc.) to present the results of B-WaterSmart.

ICS-UL regularly attends annual and bi-annual conferences of SSH organisations such as the International Sociological Association (ISA) and the European Sociological Association (ESA), where the results of the SSH work developed within B-WaterSmart, and especially within WP5 (social acceptance and governance), will continue to be disseminated.

In terms of scientific publications and in addition to the Open Access publications already available in the project, VERITAS is planning to perform one paper submission for peer review to an international journal by the end of the project and at least another publication after the project closure. It intends to continue to include B-WaterSmart in the annual Agenda del Riciclo. This was already done for the year 2023 (1st volume; 2nd volume) and is planned for 2024 (publication in autumn 2024).

The Lisbon Municipality team is preparing the following publications:

- Viegas R.M.C., Figueiredo D., Mesquita E., Charrua S., Costa C., Lourinho R., Rosa M.J. Pilot demonstration of direct potable reuse for beer production.
- Cardoso M.A., Silva C., Alegre H., Rosa M.J. et al. Strategic planning in water management organizations towards a water smart society
- Cardoso M.A., Rosa M.J., Ribeiro R. et al. B-Water smart policy and regulation recommendations to accelerate transition to a water-smarter society
- Lisbon LL team. Addressing smart-water challenges in Lisbon: the B-WaterSmart technical and digital solutions
- Ribeiro R., Andrade D., Vitorino D., Rosa M.J. Make it easier to assess the risks for water reuse in non-potable uses.

Within WP5 there has been a collaborative work that has resulted in joint publications being prepared by several partners across different LLs. One of these publications was presented and discussed at the 15th Sustainability Transitions Conference in Oslo in June 2024, and is due for submission to a peer-reviewed journal soon, with focus on LL Bodø and Flanders (SINTEF, KWR, ICS-UL):

- Damman, S., Glotzbach, R., Gomes, C., Haugland, B. T. Challenges and opportunities in transitions governance: the case for mainstreaming nature-based solutions

Other WP5 papers that were being prepared for submission at the time of this deliverable are:

- Gomes, C., Rebelo, M., Melo, M., “Social acceptance for water-smart solutions in 6 European regions”
- Gomes, C., Salvetti, M., Schmidt, L. “Analysis of water governance models across 6 case studies based on the OECD framework”
- Melo, M., Gomes, C., Schmidt, L., “Social acceptance of water reuse in Lisbon and Alicante” (this publication is related to a PhD thesis that is also being submitted through B-WaterSmart, expected to be submitted at University of Lisbon until December 2024).

Research partners will continue to communicate and disseminate about project methods and results in their academic teaching to the engineers and scientists of the future, through lectures/seminars for under- and postgraduates.

The ICS-UL team is directly involved in teaching at PhD and master programmes where the results of B-WaterSmart will continue to be discussed in lectures related to environmental sociology, sustainability practices and climate adaptation, most notably within the PhD programme on Climate Change and Sustainable Development Policies. The SHIFT research group (Environment, Territory and Society) also regularly organises international seminars and webinars where the topics of circular economy, water sustainability and climate adaptation will be a central focus.

The results of the project will also continue to be disseminated through the ICS partnerships and research networks, such as the Green Deal Net. Other partnerships at the European and international

level will be an opportunity for promoting B-WaterSmart and exchanging experiences on water sustainability. In November 2024, a team of three researchers from three Brazilian universities (University of Campina Grande, State University of Paraíba, and University of Blumenau) will visit ICS for joint activities on water governance, including lectures, seminars, and technical visits. Also in November, as a partner of the Ibero-American Network for Environmental Studies (RIDES), ICS-UL will be involved in the organisation of an international congress on socio-environmental studies with University of Alicante (Institute of Water and Environmental Sciences), where the B-WaterSmart project will be presented.

Regarding the digital research data generated by the research activities, the partners will deposit new publications in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) the data. This includes associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible, and other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan' (DMP). They will also provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the partners and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves). The management of these data will be made in accordance with the Project's DMP and in compliance with the EU Intellectual Property Rights Regulations.

This will be done strictly in conformity with the obligations of maintaining anonymity, confidentiality, security and protecting personal data. Data archiving will make use of the services provided by OpenAire (www.openaire.eu), ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/>) or CESSDA Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (<https://www.cessda.eu/>).

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